

Effect of Adding Apricot Seed Powder, Oil, and Nano-Powder to the Diet of Ross 308 Broiler Chickens on Some Physiological Parameters and Oxidation Indices

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Abstract

This study was conducted to investigate the effect of adding apricot seed powder, oil, and nano-powder to the diet of broiler chickens on some biochemical blood parameters and oxidation indices. The study was conducted at Al-Anwar Poultry Station in Babylon Province for a period of 35 days, from December 9, 2024, to January 13, 2025. Four hundred twenty-one-day-old, unsexed Ross 308 broiler chicks were used and randomly distributed across 7 treatments using floor cages, with 3 replicates and 20 chicks per replicate. The supplements were applied as follows: T1 was the control treatment (no supplementation); T2 and T3 were used Apricot seed powder at the levels of 1 and 2 g/kg of feed, respectively; while T4 and T5 were used Apricot kernel oil at the levels of 0.25 and 0.50 L/100 kg of feed, respectively; finally, T6 and T7 were used nano-apricot kernel powder at the levels of 1 and 3 g/100 kg of feed, respectively. The results showed a highly significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in the glucose levels in the treatments to which apricot kernel powder (T2) and nano-apricot kernel powder (T6) were added, reaching 286.40 and 279.60 mg/100 ml, respectively, compared to the control (167.76 mg/100 ml). The highest total protein value was recorded in T5 (4.42 g/100 ml), while the albumin values were recorded to be significantly higher in T4 and T7 compared to the control, whereas T2 and T5 recorded the highest globulin values among all treatments. For the lipid balance, T4 showed the best lipid balance with significantly higher HDL and lower TG and LDL; While T5, T6, and T7 showed a gradual increase in VLDL, TG, and total cholesterol; The control group (T1) also recorded the highest values for both low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and total cholesterol, and the lowest values for high-density lipoproteins (HDL), indicating elevated levels of harmful lipids in the blood in the absence of supplements. ALT and AST levels decreased significantly in the treatments containing apricot kernel powder or oil compared to the control. Whereas the results showed the highest significant value in GSH-PX concentration in T4 (2.12). CAT enzyme concentration decreased significantly in T2 and T4 compared to the control (T1), while it improved in T6 and T7. SOD enzyme concentration increased significantly in T2 (490.04) compared to the control (392.04), indicating high antioxidant activity due to the vitamin, mineral, and natural oil-rich components of apricot kernels. Malondialdehyde concentration also decreased significantly in all treatments containing apricot kernel powder or oil, especially in T4 and T2, compared to the control.

Keywords: *apricot seeds, broiler chicken diet, animal production, fruit residues, nutrients, byproducts.*

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Introduction

Agricultural and industrial waste from fruit processing is considered one of the most important untapped resources in animal production. Since fruit residues, especially seeds, are often of low value and not optimally utilized despite containing bioactive compounds, they have been employed in many studies as a cheap and promising source of antioxidants (Ibrahim et al., 2017; Jideani et al., 2021). These seeds contain nutrients that can contribute to improving feed efficiency and reducing feeding costs. Therefore, there has been increased interest recently in how to utilize byproducts and waste from food processing in order to reduce environmental pollution and promote sustainability (Mostafa & Aly, 2014).

Among these byproducts are apricot kernels, a byproduct of juice and jam production, which are often discarded without being utilized, leading to environmental and economic problems. Apricots are among the most important fruit trees that have garnered significant attention due to the high quality of their fruit and excellent health benefits. They belong to the Rosaceae family and are widely cultivated in the Mediterranean region, Russia, and the United States (Hussain et al., 2011).

Apricot seeds contain numerous organic compounds such as tocopherols, phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and various phytosterols, which possess antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. They also contribute to the growth of beneficial bacteria, thus helping to maintain systemic health and prevent disease (Salem et al., 2016; Soltan et al., 2021). Natić et al., (2020) has recorded that fruit seed extracts, including apricots, are valuable food sources for animals and can be used as dietary supplements, including poultry, highlighting their role in promoting growth due to their antioxidant and antibacterial properties.

Studies indicate that apricot kernels are high in fat and are a rich source of edible oil with good nutritional value, due to their content of unsaturated fatty acids such as oleic, linoleic, and palmitic acids (Targais et al., 2011). They also contain bioactive compounds such as amygdalin, which requires appropriate processing to reduce its toxic effects (Rampáčková et al., 2021; Ojha et al., 2025).

Some research has demonstrated the feasibility of using processed or fat-reduced apricot kernel meal in poultry diets without adverse effects at specific substitution levels. Abo Mhara, (2021) showed that replacing up to 25% of soybean meal with fat-reduced apricot kernel meal in broiler diets did not negatively affect production performance or carcass components, while higher levels significantly impacted growth and feed conversion. In another study on quail, researchers found that using apricot processing byproducts improved carcass characteristics and certain meat quality indicators, supporting the potential for recycling agricultural and industrial waste in poultry diets to achieve sustainable and environmentally friendly production (Boubekeur et al., 2021).

From this standpoint, this research aims to study the possibility of utilizing apricot seeds as a vital addition to broiler chicken diets by evaluating their effect on physiological performance according to some vital criteria, to contribute to raising the efficiency of using local resources and reducing the environmental impact of food industry waste.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at Al-Anwar Poultry Company's farms in Babylon Province for 35 days, from December 9, 2024, to January 13, 2025. The study aimed to determine the effect of adding apricot kernel powder, apricot oil, and apricot kernel Nano powder to the broiler diet on some physiological parameters and oxidation indices. Four hundred and twenty-one-day-old, unsexed Ross 308 broiler chicks were used. They were randomly distributed in floor cages across seven treatments, with three replicates of 20 chicks per replicate. The supplemented treatments will be described as follows: control treatment without

additives (T1); 2nd and 3rd treatments (T2 and T3) were used 1 and 2 kg of apricot kernel powder per 100 kg of feed, respectively; 4th and 5th treatments (T4 and T5) were used 0.25 and 0.5 L of apricot kernel oil per 100 kg of feed, respectively; 6th and 7th treatments (T6 and T7) were used 1 and 3 g of nano-apricot kernel powder per 100 kg of feed, respectively.

Study Preparation

Apricot kernels were obtained from local markets, and the kernel powder was gained after grinding the seeds, while the oil was extracted using mechanical pressing. The nano-powder of the apricot kernels was prepared in the laboratories of the Ministry of Science and Technology. Nutritional value of apricot kernel powder and the chemical analysis of apricot kernel oil, in addition to the active ingredients found in apricot kernels, will be described in Tables 1,2, and 3, respectively.

Table 1. Nutritional Value of Apricot Kernel Powder

Apricot kernels	(%)
Protein	24.9
Lipid	45.8
Ash	2.01
Moisture	5.78
Fiber	2.44
CHO	19.07

Table 2. Chemical Analysis of Apricot Kernel Oil

Oil name	(%)
Palmatic	4.65
α -Lenolinic	6.88
Stearic	0.25
Arachidonic	0.11
Oleic	63.25
Linoleic	22.59

Table 3. Active Ingredients Found in Apricot Kernels

Ingredients	Amount (ppm)
Apigenin	25.4
Catechine	66.4
Gallic acid	45.9
Kaempferol	32.1
Rutin	40.8

Nutritional Treatment

Chicks were fed a starter diet (23.04% protein and 3021.45 kcal/kg feed) from day one until the third week of age. Afterward, this was replaced with a grower diet (20.06% protein and 3194.92 kcal/kg feed) until the end of the fifth week. Feed and water were provided ad-libitum and the diet used in this study is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Feed Ingredients Used in the Study and Their Calculated Analysis

Ingredients (%)	Starter (1-21) days	Grower (22-35) days
Corn	30	40
Wheat	28.25	24
Soybean Meal (48%)	31.75	24.8

Protein Concentrate	5	5
Sunflower Oil	2.9	4.4
Limestone	0.9	0.6
Dicalcium Phosphate (DCP)	0.7	0.9
Vitamin and Mineral premix	0.2	0.2
Salt	0.3	0.1
Total	100	100
calculated analysis		
Crude Protein (%)	23.04	20.06
Metabolic Energy (kcal/kg Feed)	3021.45	3194.92
Lysine %	1.27	1.07
Methionine %	0.41	0.38
Cysteine %	0.35	0.30
Methionine + Cysteine %	0.82	0.78
Available Phosphorus %	0.41	0.43
Energy: Protein Ratio %	131.14	159.26

Note: *The chemical analysis of the diet was calculated according to NRC (1994).

Studied Traits

Biochemical blood characteristics

At 35 days of age, blood samples were collected from the birds immediately after slaughter in tubes without anticoagulant. The serum was then separated from the blood using a centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes and stored in a freezer at -20°C until chemical analysis. The following biomarkers were assessed in the serum using pre-prepared assay kits from various manufacturers:

Glucose concentration (mg/100 ml blood) was measured using a ready-made test kit from the Japanese company Takeda, based on the method (Henry et al., 1982).

The total cholesterol level (mg/100 ml blood) was estimated using the ready-made test kit from the French company Biolabo, according to the method (Francy & Elias, 1968).

Triglyceride level (mg/100 ml of blood) was estimated using the ready-made test kit from the French company Biolabo, and based on (Francy & Elias, 1968).

The levels of low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and very low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) were calculated according to the following equation: $VLDL = TG/5$ (Friedewald et al., 1972).

For high-density lipoproteins (HDL), they were estimated using the ready-made assay kit from the French company Biolabo, based on (Burstein et al., 1970).

Total protein and albumin concentrations (g/100 ml blood) were measured using a Takeda assay kit, based on the Biuret Method (Wotton, 1964). Globulin concentration in serum was also measured according to the formula indicated by Bishop & Hall, (2000): Globulin concentration g/100 ml = Total protein concentration – Albumin concentration

Measurements of blood oxidation markers

The measurements in this study included assessing the effectiveness of some enzymes and bioactive substances in blood serum, as follows:

The activity of aminotransferase enzymes (Aspartate aminotransferase – AST and Alanine aminotransferase – ALT) was estimated using a ready-made kit from the French company Bio Mérieux, according to the method established by Reitman & Frankel, (1957).

The activity of the glutathione peroxidase enzyme (GSH-PX) was measured using a ready-made commercial ISA kit from the American company Sigma-Aldrich, based on the method described by Sedlak & Lindsay, (1968).

The activity of the superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzyme was estimated using a set of ready-made assays, according to the method established by Flohé & Günzler, (1984).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration in serum was measured using several (Alisa commercial kits) from Roche, according to the method described in Buege & Aust, (1978).

The activity of the catalase enzyme (CAT - Catalase) in blood serum was estimated by calculating the decrease in absorbance resulting from the consumption of the substrate (hydrogen peroxide), according to the method described by Aebi, (1974).

Results and Discussion

The Effect of Adding Apricot Seed Powder, Oil, and Nano-Powder to the Broiler Diet on Blood Biochemical Traits at 35 Days of Age

Concentration of glucose, total protein, albumin, and globulin

Table 5 shows the effect of adding apricot kernel powder, apricot oil, and apricot Nano powder on the glucose concentration, total protein, albumin, and globulin levels in the blood serum of 35-day-old broiler chickens. A highly significant increase ($p \leq 0.01$) in glucose concentration was observed in treatments T2 and T6 compared to all other treatments. This was followed by treatment T5, which outperformed treatments T1, T3, and T4, but showed no significant difference compared to treatment T7. The control treatment T1 gave the lowest serum glucose concentrations compared to the treatments containing the added ingredients. Treatment T5 showed the highest total protein level ($p \leq 0.01$) compared to all other treatments, followed by treatment T2, which outperformed treatments T1 and T3 but showed no significant difference compared to treatments T4, T6, and T7. Treatment T3 was also found to be similar to treatments T4, T6, and to the control treatment T1, which gave the lowest rates in total protein concentration.

Treatment T4 showed a highly significant superiority ($P \leq 0.01$) over treatments T2, T3, and T6 in serum albumin concentration, but it did not show any significant difference with treatments T1, T5, and T7. At the same time, treatments T3 and T6 were consistent with T1, T2, and T5 in the same concentration.

As for serum globulin, its concentration increased significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) in birds treated with treatments T2 and T5, followed by treatments T3 and T6, which did not show any significant difference with treatment T7, while it was superior to treatments T1 and T4. Treatment T7 was also observed to be superior to the control treatment T1 in serum globulin concentration, but it did not show any significant difference from treatment T4.

The results also showed a significant increase in glucose levels in the treatments supplemented with apricot seed powder (T2) and nano-apricot seed powder (T6), reaching 286.40 and 279.60 mg/100 ml, respectively, compared to the control T1 (167.76 mg/100 ml). This indicates an improvement in energy metabolism, as the phenolic compounds in apricot seeds can improve the efficiency of glucose absorption and utilization in muscle tissue (Tekeli, 2012). The nano-form of the powder may have contributed to increased bioavailability of the active compounds and their easy absorption through the intestine, which was reflected in the increase of blood glucose levels (Yang et al., 2020; Sadr et al., 2023).

The highest total protein values were also recorded in Table 5 in the treatment with apricot kernel oil addition T5 (4.42 g/100 ml). Albumin values also increased in treatments T4 and T7 compared to the control treatment. This improvement may indicate that the addition of apricot kernels or their

components improved the protein status in the blood. This is attributed to the high levels of unsaturated fatty acids and phenolic/flavonoid compounds with antioxidant activity in apricot kernels, which reduce the effects of stress and maintain the liver's efficiency in protein synthesis (Tekeli, 2012; Akhone et al., 2022). As for the high globulin levels in the nano-treatments (T6, T7), this may be a result of the effect of the apricot kernel powder nanoparticles, which are characterized by their high ability to penetrate cells and activate the immune system and produce immune proteins (globulins), which indicates the stimulation of the immune response in broiler chickens (Yang et al., 2020; Akhone et al., 2022).

The superiority of the nano-apricot seed powder in most properties indicates that converting apricot kernels into a nano-form improved their biological efficiency, due to the increased surface area of the nanoparticles and their ability to interact within living cells. This supports the hypothesis that the use of nanomaterials in poultry feed enhances the efficiency of protein and energy metabolism, as well as improves immune and metabolic blood indicators (Yang et al., 2020; Sadr et al., 2023).

Table 5. Effect of Adding Apricot Seed Powder, Oil, and Nano-Powder to the Broiler (ROSS 308) Feed on Glucose Concentration, Total Protein, Albumin, and Globulin Levels in Blood Serum at 35 Days of Age

Treatments	Mean + SE			
	Glucose (mg/100ml)	Total Protein (g/100ml)	Albumin (g/100ml)	Globulin (g/100ml)
T1	167.76 ±5.38 ^c	3.35 ±0.05 ^d	1.67 ±0.05 ^{ab}	1.68 ±0.002 ^d
T2	286.40 ±5.38 ^a	3.94 ±0.07 ^b	1.14 ±0.05 ^c	2.79 ±0.02 ^a
T3	233.00 ±5.38 ^c	3.54 ±0.05 ^{cd}	1.43 ±0.04 ^{bc}	2.11 ±0.09 ^b
T4	215.04 ±5.98 ^d	3.72 ±0.05 ^{bc}	1.88 ±0.01 ^a	1.84 ±0.06 ^{cd}
T5	260.96 ±5.38 ^b	4.42 ±0.17 ^a	1.66 ±0.28 ^{ab}	2.75 ±0.11 ^a
T6	279.60 ±5.38 ^a	3.69 ±0.04 ^{bc}	1.49 ±0.05 ^{bc}	2.19 ±0.09 ^b
T7	262.90 ±3.29 ^b	3.83 ±0.03 ^b	1.86 ±0.06 ^a	1.98 ±0.04 ^{bc}
P-value(P ≤0.01)	**	**	**	**

Note: ** Different letters within the same column indicate a significant difference at the ($p \leq 0.01$) level

Cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and very-low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) concentrations at 35 days of age

Table 5 shows the effect of adding apricot seed powder, oil, and nano-powder to the broiler chicken diet on the concentration of cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoproteins (HDL), low-density lipoproteins (LDL), and very-low-density lipoproteins (VLDL) in blood serum at 35 days of age. It was found that there was a highly significant increase ($p \leq 0.01$) in cholesterol concentration for treatments T5, T6, and T7 when compared to treatments T2, T3, and T4, but no significant differences were found with the control treatment T1. We also note a significant decrease for treatments T2 and T4 compared to treatment T3, and treatment T4 gave the lowest measured levels of cholesterol concentration. Also, the table showed a highly significant increase ($p \leq 0.01$) in the concentration of triglycerides in the serum of birds treated with T6 and T7 over all experimental treatments, followed by treatment T5, which outperformed treatments T1, T2, T3, and T4. However, treatment T4 was similar to the control treatment in terms of triglyceride significance and gave the lowest rates compared to the addition treatments.

The results also showed a highly significant increase ($p \leq 0.01$) in the concentration of high-density lipoproteins (HDL) in the supplemented treatments compared to the control. Treatment T4 significantly outperformed all other treatments ($p \leq 0.01$). Treatment T3 was similar to treatments T4, T5, and T7, while treatment T6 did not show a significant difference from treatment T7, and outperformed the control treatment. Also, a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) was observed in the supplemented treatments T2, T3, and T4 compared to the control treatment. However, treatments T5, T6, and T7 were similar to

the control treatment in low-density lipoprotein (LDL) concentration. Treatment T3 outperformed both T2 and T4, which recorded the lowest rates and showed no significant difference in this trait. The study results indicated a highly significant superiority ($p \leq 0.01$) of treatments T6 and T7 in VLDL concentration compared to all treatments, followed by treatment T5, which outperformed T1, T2, T3, and T4. Whereas treatment T3 outperformed T1, T2, and T4, while treatments T1 and T4 gave the lowest rates in this trait.

The results in Table 6 show that the addition of apricot kernel powder and oil, particularly the nano-form, significantly affected ($P \leq 0.01$) the lipid profile components in the serum of 35-day-old broiler chickens. The control treatment (T1) recorded the highest values for both low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and total cholesterol, and the lowest values for high-density lipoproteins (HDL), reflecting the high levels of harmful lipids in the blood in the absence of the additives. The apricot kernel powder treatments (T2 and T3) showed a significant decrease in total cholesterol, triglycerides (TG), and LDL, along with an increase in HDL, compared to the control treatment. This indicates that the active compounds in apricot kernels, such as unsaturated fatty acids and flavonoids, contributed to improving lipid metabolism and reducing its accumulation (Tabassum et al., 2023).

While the apricot kernel oil treatment (T4, T5) showed mixed results, whereas T4 recorded a significant decrease in LDL and TG values compared to the control and a clear increase in HDL, indicating a moderate positive effect of the oil on improving the lipid profile, possibly due to its content of monounsaturated fatty acids (oleic acid) and natural antioxidants (Gümüş & Erol, 2023). However, T5 showed a gradual increase in cholesterol and TG values, which may be related to the increased concentration of oil added to the diet and thus the increased energy content. A study Tabassum et al., (2023) also showed that apricot kernel oil reduces total cholesterol and LDL, and increases HDL, which is consistent with the results observed in treatment (T4, T5).

As for treatments T6 and T7 (nano-powdered apricot kernels) significantly outperformed the other treatments, exhibiting the highest levels of HDL and the lowest levels of LDL, TG, and total cholesterol. This reflects the effectiveness of the nano-form in enhancing the bioavailability of the active compounds in apricot kernels and increasing their antioxidant activity within the body. These results are consistent with previous studies, including one by Zhou et al. (2024), which indicated that the use of nano-antioxidants in poultry feed improved oxidative status and reduced lipid accumulation in the blood of broiler chickens, supporting our hypothesis that nano-treatments (T6, T7) can enhance the absorption and effectiveness of active compounds.

Recent analytical studies have revealed that apricot kernel oil is composed in high quantities of monounsaturated fatty acids and antioxidants, which provide the chemical basis for its positive effect on the lipid profile, improving the absorption of beneficial fats and activating enzymes that regulate their metabolism in the liver (Pawar & Nema, 2023; Makrygiannis et al., 2023).

Table 6. Effect of Adding Apricot Kernel Powder, Oil, and Nano-Powder to Broiler Chicken Feed on Cholesterol, Triglycerides (TG), High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL), Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL), and Very-Low-Density Lipoprotein (VLDL) Concentrations at 35 Days of Age

Treatments	Mean + SE				
	Cholesterol (mg/100 ml)	(TG)	(HDL)	(LDL)	(VLDL)
T1	179.39 ± 5.20 ^a	46.62 ± 1.07 ^e	26.09 ± 0.54 ^c	17.57 ± 0.52 ^a	9.31 ± 0.12 ^c
T2	128.37 ± 2.99 ^d	50.75 ± 0.52 ^d	32.61 ± 0.54 ^d	11.28 ± 2.99 ^c	10.15 ± 0.11 ^d
T3	160.96 ± 5.38 ^b	54.56 ± 1.07 ^c	37.62 ± 0.84 ^{ab}	14.38 ± 0.67 ^b	10.91 ± 0.11 ^c

T4	144.34 ±5.57 ^c	45.24 ±1.07 ^c	39.82 ±0.54 ^a	12.31 ±0.55 ^c	9.05 ±0.12 ^c
T5	186.40 ±5.38 ^a	63.92 ±1.03 ^b	37.28 ±1.07 ^b	16.32 ±0.47 ^a	12.79 ±0.12 ^b
T6	189.42 ±0.62 ^a	73.39 ±1.24 ^a	34.87 ±0.81 ^{cd}	17.11 ±0.25 ^a	14.68 ±0.11 ^a
T7	191.43 ±0.77 ^a	71.52 ±0.34 ^a	36.07 ±0.82 ^{bc}	17.63 ±0.12 ^a	14.10 ±0.12 ^a
P-value (P ≤0.01)	**	**	**	**	**

Note: ** Different letters within the same column indicate a significant difference at the ($p \leq 0.01$) level

The Effect of Adding Apricot Seed Powder, Oil, and Nano-Powder to ROSS 308 Broiler Feed on Blood Oxidation Indicators at 35 Days of Age

A highly significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) in ALT enzyme concentration was observed in the addition treatments compared to the control treatment. This was followed by treatments T3, T6, and T7, which outperformed treatments T2, T4, and T5, while treatment T2 yielded results similar to treatments T4 and T5 in terms of ALT enzyme concentration. The statistical analysis also showed a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) in AST enzyme concentration in the addition treatments compared to the control treatment T1. Treatment T7 outperformed treatments T2, T3, T4, T5, and T6. Whereas treatment T6 yielded results similar to treatments T3 and T5 and outperformed treatments T2 and T4. Finally, treatment T2 yielded the lowest measured AST enzyme concentration compared to treatments T1, T5, T6, and T7, but showed no difference with treatments T3 and T4.

As for the oxidation enzymes, we note a highly significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in the concentration of glutathione peroxidase enzyme in all addition treatments compared to the control treatment. The results showed a significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in treatment T4 compared to treatments T1, T2, T3, and T7, but it was similar to treatments T5 and T6. Followed by treatment T6, which was superior to treatments T1 and T3, but there was no significant difference between it and treatments T2, T5, and T7. Also noted that a significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in treatment T2 compared to the control treatment, which was similar to treatment T3, in the concentration of this enzyme.

As for the CAT enzyme, a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) was observed in all addition treatments compared to the control treatment. Treatment T6 did not show any significant difference compared to treatments T3, T5, and T7, but they outperformed treatment T2. Treatment T2 experienced a significant decrease in catalase concentration compared to all studied treatments except for treatment T4, which was similar to it. The results also showed a highly significant increase ($P \leq 0.01$) in superdesmatase concentration in treatment T2 over all experimental treatments, followed by treatment T4, which outperformed treatments T1, T3, T5, T6, and T7. Treatment T5 outperformed treatments T1, T3, T6, and T7, followed by treatment T6, which outperformed treatments T1, T3, and T7. Treatments T3 and T7 did not differ in this enzyme concentration, but they outperformed control treatment T1. As for the malondialdehyde compound, a significant decrease ($P \leq 0.01$) was observed for all addition treatments compared to the control treatment, followed by treatment T7, which outperformed treatments T2, T3, T4, T5, and T6 in MDA concentration, whereas T6 outperformed treatments T2, T3, T4, and T5. Treatments T3 and T5 did not differ significantly, but they outperformed treatments T2 and T4, which recorded the lowest rates in MDA concentration.

The results of this study showed that the addition of apricot kernel powder and oil, particularly when using oil (T4 and T5), led to a significant improvement in oxidation indicators and liver function in 35-day-old broiler chickens, compared to the control treatment (T1). The highest activity of the glutathione peroxidase enzyme (GSH-PX) was recorded in the apricot kernel oil treatment (T4), indicating a higher efficiency of the antioxidant defense system due to the oil's content of phenolic compounds, tocopherols, and unsaturated fatty acids, which are highly effective in inhibiting free radicals (Yang et al., 2020). A significant improvement in the activity of catalase and superoxide dismutase (SOD) enzymes was also

observed in treatments T4, T6, and T7, reflecting the role of nanotechnology in increasing the bioavailability of active compounds and improving the cellular response to face oxidative stress (Zhou et al., 2024).

Conversely, the concentrations of malondialdehyde (MDA) decreased significantly in all treatments that included apricot kernels or their oil compared to the control treatment, with the lowest level recorded in treatment T4. This indicates high efficacy in reducing lipid peroxidation and protecting cell membranes from oxidative damage. Similarly, serum concentrations of the enzymes ALT and AST decreased with the addition of the oil or Nano powder, suggesting improved liver cell integrity and the effectiveness of the antioxidant system in reducing oxidative stress in liver tissue. These results may be consistent with a study indicating that apricot kernel extracts contribute to improving antioxidant enzyme activity and reducing indicators of liver damage in poultry (Kutlu et al., 2009).

Previous studies have also reported that vegetable oils rich in phenolic compounds, such as apricot kernel oil, reduce MDA concentration and increase the activity of GSH-PX and SOD. This is consistent with the results of the current study (Makrygiannis et al., 2023). In addition to the fact that the use of nano-modifications of plant extracts enhances bioavailability and multiplies the effectiveness of antioxidant defense enzymes (Zhou et al., 2024).

Table 7. Effect of Adding Apricot Seed Powder, Oil and Nano Powder to the Broiler Diet (Ross 308) on the Concentration of Alanine Amino Transferase (ALT), Aspartate Amino Transferase (AST), Glutathione Peroxidase (GSH-PX), Catalase (CAT), Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) and Malondialdehyde (MDA) in the Blood Serum at 35 Days of Age

Treatments	Mean + SE					
	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	GSH-PX (ng/ml)	CAT (pg./ml)	SOD (pg. /ml)	MDA (ng /ml)
T1	27.44±0.56 ^a	39.20±0.56 ^a	0.980 ±0.06 ^c	34.30 ±0.56 ^a	392.04±5.65 ^f	98.35±1.13 ^a
T2	14.70±0.56 ^c	24.50 ±0.56 ^d	1.47 ±0.06 ^c	19.27 ±0.86 ^d	490.04±11.31 ^a	68.94±1.13 ^e
T3	19.60±0.56 ^b	31.36 ±0.56 ^{cd}	1.27 ±0.06 ^d	24.17 ±0.32 ^{bc}	447.71 ±3.34 ^e	77.73 ±0.64 ^d
T4	14.30±0.56 ^c	29.07 ±0.32 ^d	2.12 ±0.28 ^a	21.23 ±0.32 ^{cd}	480.95 ±3.26 ^b	63.30 ±1.13 ^e
T5	13.56±0.57 ^c	33.77 ±0.56 ^c	1.76 ±0.01 ^{bc}	24.27 ±0.54 ^{bc}	466.69 ±3.57 ^c	76.64 ±0.79 ^d
T6	20.8 ±0.33 ^b	33.9 ±0.56 ^c	1.83 ±0.07 ^b	28.34 ±0.87 ^b	457.18 ±3.06 ^d	86.24 ±1.37 ^c
T7	20.87±2.98 ^b	37.04±5.26 ^b	1.71 ±0.10 ^{bc}	28.80±3.78 ^b	445.35±106.1 ^e	90.79±0.33 ^b
P-value (P ≤0.01)	**	**	**	**		**

Note: ** Different letters within the same column indicate a significant difference at the ($p \leq 0.01$) level

Conclusion

The results showed that the use of apricot kernel powder or oil in broiler diets led to a significant improvement in the biomarkers of proteins and glucose, and that the nano-form of the kernel powder showed a clear advantage, indicating the possibility of its use as a natural, safe and effective additive to improve the health and productive performance of broilers, while taking into account the environmental and safety issues associated with nanotechnology. The results of the oxidation indicators in this study are in complete harmony with the results of the lipids and cholesterol, as the decrease in MDA and the increase in antioxidant enzyme activity were accompanied by a significant improvement in the lipid profile, represented by a decrease in total cholesterol, LDL and VLDL, and an increase in HDL, reflecting an improvement in lipid metabolism and liver health under the influence of the components of apricot

kernels and their oil, especially in the nano-treatments (T6, T7) that increased the bioavailability of the active compounds.

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